

Nutrient Specific Intervention in Pregnancy: The Role of Family Welfare Empowerment Program

Dewa Ayu Putu Ratna Juwita^{1*}, Luh Gede Pradnyawati², Anny Eka Pratiwi³, Made
Indra Wijaya⁴

^{1,2,3,4}Department of Public Health Health and Preventive Medicine, Faculty of medicine and Health Science,
Warmadewa University

*Corresponding email: Dewa Ayu Putu Ratna Juwita. dapratnajuwita@gmail.com

Abstract

Introduction: malnutrition is a greatest global health issue on child health focus. Dietary pattern intake in pregnancy is one of the determinant factors on this fundamental problem. Mother's knowledge, attitude, and behavior, also dairy intake and diversity are the key factors impacted. **Purpose:** this study purposed to know the effectiveness of family welfare empowerment program on their attitude, behavior, knowledge, dietary intake and diversity. **Methods:** this ia a Quazi-experimental included 109 pregnant population mother in Payangan district between July-December 2023. We have implemented family welfare empowerment program to give education and training program in pregnancy for three months to increase their level of knowledge, attitude, and behavior on nutrition choice. **Result:** The mean age of intervention group was 23.59 years old and 24.78 of the control group. There was difference increase in knowledge scores 87% (p0.026), attitude 79% (p0.02), and behavior 73.8% (p0.00) domain before and after the program significantly. The program is effective to increase the risk of high knowledge and high attitude of pregnancy mother 5.219 times and 4.400 times compare with mothers who didn't get the program significantly. **Conclusion:** this program could be an important role associated with an increase of knowledge, behavior and attitude in pregnancy women. This program could be well managed comprehensively at community to accelerate prevention on malnutrition program.

Keywords: malnutrition, family welfare, knowledge, behavior, attitude, dietary pattern

INTRODUCTION

Stunting defined as an impaired of growth and development that affect children under two years old. Stunted in children are defined if their height for age is more than two standard deviations (below Child Growth Standards median of WHO Graph). Linear growth in early childhood is a best marker of healthy growth given its association with disease, cognitive, and children's productivity. Stunting should be control to prevent a number adverse effects on child's development cycle. Stunting in the first 1000 days of life has adverse functional consequences including low cognitive level then educational performance, loss of productivity, low of adult wages, and increased risk of nutrition-relater chronic disease in their life. ^[1,2]

There are many determinant factors of stunting. Children experience of inadequate stimulation, chronic and

repeated malnutrition, poor nutrition, infection, house hold factor like mother's knowledge, attitude, and behavior, also dairy intake and diversity are the key factors impacted. Wrong dietary pattern in pregnancy reported as a strong predictor and played an important role of growth and development of 1.000 days first life. It caused by chronic or repeated malnutrition that linked with poor maternal nutrition in pregnancy. Dietary pattern intake in pregnancy is one of the determinant factors on this fundamental problem. ^[3,4]

Malnutrition is a greatest global health issue on child health focus, and stunting is one of the types of malnutrition during child that affect child's height and their development. A malnourished mothers are at potent risk of giving birth to malnourished babies who also at greater risk of stunting. Malnutrition and household factors and families are factors

that related of it. Eat of a healthy diet in pregnancy has begun to provoke a fundamental issue to covered. A balanced

Family is a nuclear system in providing nutrients for pregnancy mother. Family household characteristic was identified as a role factors that affect stunting.^[7,8] Family factors such as family system, social-cultural, primary caregiver/mother, and family headship were identified as being associated with stunting. Primary caregiver/mother intervention in nutrition aspect focused on preparing adequate dietary intake during pregnancy due to the quality of pregnancy diet. Pregnancy diet divided into two categories: dietary restriction and excessive diet. Dietary restriction referred to under-nutrient and excessive diet referred to metabolic impairment. Dietary restriction and excessive diet are wrong dietary pattern in pregnancy and a risk factor stunting^[7,8].

Family welfare empowerment program is an initiative interventional program for family to support a healthy dietary pattern in pregnancy. Through empowerment program, their participant can be increase and involving them as a nourishment kader to support their attitude, behavior, knowledge, dietary intake and diversity nutrition. The focus on their participant can demonstrate efforts to address the challenge of full nourish children.^[9,10] This study aimed to know the effectiveness of family welfare empowerment program on pregnancy.

METHODE

This was a Quazi experimental study, included 109 population of pregnant mothers in Payangan district between July-December 2023 with 64 eligible

diet in pregnancy recommended to be a specific intervention to prevent stunting in children.^[5,6]

sample for both intervention and control groups using cluster sampling. We have implemented family welfare empowerment program to give education and training program in pregnancy for three months to increase their level of knowledge, attitude, and behavior on nutrition. We provided a nutrition module, pre-test and post-test, and focus group discussion using purposive sampling to asses their level regarding nutrition status in pregnancy. Pretest was conducted before the intervention, while posttest evaluations were carried out after the education sessions concluded.

We use questionnaire as an instrument to know the level of knowledge, attitude, and behavior o pregnancy diet to collect data. This knowledge questionnaire had undergone validity and reliability testing, with a calculated r-value lower than the critical r-value (0.2). The attitude questionnaire was validated adopted by the researcher with the same validity threshold ($r < 0.3$) and the reliability scores was 0.820 for knowledge and 0.890 for attitudes.

The module developed by the researcher, consists of four components domain: knowledge of nutrition, pregnancy, proper diet of pregnancy and the source nutrient of local foods. The program conducted in Payangan Village using lecture, discussion, test, and observation method. Observation and evaluation every month were held to analyse the knowledge, attitude, and behavior on pregnancy dietary pattern.

between two group is showed in Table 2.

Table 1 Sociodemographic Characteristic

Sample Characteristic	Group		n (%)	p-value
	Intervention Group (N=32)	Control Group (N=32)		
Age				0.941
15-30 yo	23 (71.88%)	30 (93.75%)	53 (82.81%)	
> 30 yp	9 (28.13%)	2 (6.25%)	11 (17.19%)	
Mean ± SD	23,59±2,06	24,78±1,11		
Education Level				0.781
Low	15 (46.88%)	10 (31.25%)	25 (39.06%)	
High	17 (53.13%)	29 (68.75%)	46 (71.88%)	
Occupation				0.167
None	20 (62.50%)	24 (75.00%)	44 (68.75%)	
Working	12 (37.50%)	8 (25.00%)	20 (31.25%)	
Income				0.321
Rp -	12 (37.50%)	8 (25.00%)	20 (31.25%)	
Rp 1,000.000-3.000.000	11 (34.37%)	9 (28.12%)	20 (31.25%)	
>Rp 3.000.000	9 (28.13%)	15 (46.88%)	24 (31.25%)	

Table 2. Comparison of Knowledge, Attitude, and Behavior after The Program

Domain	Intervention Group (N=32)	Control Group (N=32)	n (%)	OR (95%CI)	p-value
Knowledge					
High	25 (78.13%)	13 (40.63%)	38 (59.38%)	5.219 (1.249-15.196)	<0.000*
Low	7 (21.88%)	19 (59.38%)	15 (40.63%)		
Score of intervention group	87%				0.026*
Attitude					
High	22 (68.75%)	11 (34.38%)	33 (72.0%)	4,400 (1.771-10.658)	0.023*
Low	10 (31.25%)	22 (68.75%)	32 (50.0%)		
Score of intervention group	79%				0.02*
Behavior					
High	17 (46.89%)	13 (40.63%)	28 (87.5%)	1,290 (1.376-2.370)	0.076
Low	15 (53.13%)	19 (59.38%)	36 (56.25%)		
Score of intervention group	73.8%				0.00*

*significant

RESULT

The characteristic of the two group is on the Table 1. The mean age of intervention group was 23.59 years old and 24.78 of the control group. Table 1 showed that the Table 2 showed that the program is effective to increase the risk of high knowledge and high attitude of pregnancy mother 5.219 times and 4.400 times compare with mothers who didn't get the program significantly. On the other hand, this table showed that this

characteristic of the two group did not different significantly from age, education level, occupation, and income domain ($p>0.05$). The distribution of knowledge, attitude, and behavior program is could increase the risk of high behavior 1.290 times, but not significant ($p0.076$). Score of knowledge, attitude, and behavior in intervention group only showed that there is significant increase score before and after of the program.

We initiate many respondents as

purposive sampling to conduct deep interview until the information is fed up. Deep interview was expand two domain: 1) mainly food, 2) additional food with the question: 1)"*what is mainly food that you consume three days past*" and 2) *what is your supplementation for pregnancy three days past*" as below:

Mrs PAS, 23yo

" I usually consume rice three times a day. I cant live without any rice even though there is so much meat, I cant feel enough. Milk just incidental when we have enough money, tempe is better pouch. Oranges is everywhere...cheap as cips. Folic acid yes"

Mrs IKS, 35yo

" It depends on trimester of pregnancy..u know now I can't feel anything through the belly, just fruits...but common food is rice at home. Milk is not necessary at all, so does meat...corn..casava..one egg sharing with others is enough. Folic acid every day is necessary"

Mrs NS, 29yo

"I always eat rice with meat...it should be meat on the dishes. Fruits is seldom...we need rice to life, fruits just when there is a ceremony except orange....we have large land of orange trees. Meat we always have tahu and tempe...sometime chicken. Pig or cow is seldom bit folic tablet should consume."

Mrs NWA, 18yo

"Rice..tahu..tempe. We should share...eggs also. We should share to all livings inside...no other..fruits just bananas and oranges...other fruits is so expensive...I usually eat traditional cakes. Folic acid is everyday but yesterday sorry forgeted...folic yes..always"

Mrs LMG, 26 yo

"Rice is important. Rice and eggs is everyday..so does tahu and tempe. Milk..never. I have 2 children they need it more...orange is everyday. Folic acid sometime forgeted because of my

business"

The other 5 (five) respondents have the same pattern to the respondents above so we've finished the interview because the information is fed up. Rice, eggs, tahu and tempe is the most main food and fruit such oranges is the most additional food they usually consume.

DISCUSSION

Nutrition and pregnancy are significantly correlated with stunting. Pregnancy and first 1.000 days of life plays an essential role in infant life. Nutrition should be ensure to help the mother and the babies get what they need to develop. Nutrition, calory, diversity, and supplements as macro and micronutrients established the child risk of lifelong and health. Pregnancy is one of the golden period to growth and neurodevelopment.^[11,12]

Family welfare empowerment program is a voluntary of pregnancy program, include the members of family to contribute improving well-beings of pregnancy mother. It includes family planning, sharing information, doing counseling, and also education about pregnancy and nutrient.^[13] We focused on nutrient as a specific intervention in stunting framework. It is implemented for 3 (three) months evaluation, including knowledge, attitude, and behavior.

Bloom theory describe the grounded theory of health determinant: knowledge, attitude, and behavior. These three are related to others, like what is the goal of health promotion is to decrease the incident and prevalent of the disease by increase knowledge, attitude and their non-risky behavior.^[14] The determinant factors of this is sosio-demographic, such as educational level, income or economic status, occupation, and age.^[15]

This program is effective to increase the risk of high knowledge and high attitude of pregnancy mother 5.219

times and 4.400 times compare with mothers who didn't get the program significantly. This is consistent with Silk study about this program to young pregnancy mother that showed there was increased in knowledge and attitude of pregnancy mother about nutrients in 3 months repetitive training and evaluation.^[16] Wolson study showed different. Empowerment welfare program in pregnancy is not succeeded without supported by family members such as husband and also determined by sociodemographic aspects. The demographic aspects is such as: level of education and age. Level of education can impact knowledge and attitude. Knowledge gap can lead to attitude gap and contribute to risky behavior.^[17] On the other hand, this table showed that this program is could increase the risk of high behavior 1.290 times, but not significant (p0.076). Score of knowledge, attitude, and behavior in intervention group only showed that there is significant increase score before and after of the program. Repeat education on this program and intensive care is needed to gain the result. Study of Subrata performed Penta COME is effectif to decrease the prevalent of stunting in Payangan, Gianyar. Nutrient in pregnancy is one of the stimulant issues in Penta COME that covered comprehensively. This study include counseling of health diet, proper weight gain in pregnancy, and the use of micronutrient supplements as a strategy and program to catch the specific issues in dietary pattern of pregnancy.^[18]

This study also showed that there is traditional pattern (mainly consists of rice, flour, beans processed food, fruits and vegetables) including eggs as prudent dietary pattern. This two pattern provide macro and micro nutrient provide nourishment to mother and fetus. A mother diet in pregnancy and her nutrients store is needed to prevent anemia as a slight predictor of stunting and impaired

of growth and development of the children.^[19]

CONCLUSION

This program could be an important role associated with an increase of knowledge, behavior and attitude in pregnancy women. This program could be well managed comprehensively at community to accelerate prevention on malnutrition program specially for traditional diet pattern.

AKNOWLEDGEMENT

The researcher expresses gratitude to all various parties who have supported the research process, including the Head of Payangan district, Puskesmas and Faculty of Medicine and Health Sciences, Warmadewa University who facilitated the research, especially collecting data, pregnancy mother and co-ordination with the cadres. Lastly, thanks to all researchers who contributed to the study.

REFERENCES

1. Anugerah, N. M. A. N., Pradnyawati, L. G., & Pratiwi, A. E. (2024). Hubungan Tingkat Pengetahuan Ibu Tentang Gizi dengan Kejadian Stunting Balita 12-59 Bulan di Wilayah Kerja Puskesmas Tegallalang. *Aesculapius Medical Journal*, 4(2), 275-281.
2. Pradnyawati, L. G. (2022). Program kemitraan masyarakat pencegahan stunting di Desa Kerta, Kecamatan Payangan. *Warmadewa Minesterium Medical Journal*, 1(2), 50-55.
3. Um, S., Sopheab, H., Yom, A., & Muir, J. A. (2022). Trends and factors associated with anemia among pregnant women aged 15-49 years old in Cambodia: Data analysis of the Cambodia

- Demographic and Health Surveys. *medRxiv*, 2022-09.
4. Sharifi, N., Dolatian, M., Mahmoodi, Z., Abadi, F. M. N., & Mehrabi, Y. (2017). The relationship between social support and food insecurity in pregnant women: a cross-sectional study. *children*, 6, 7.
 5. Ahmed, F., Malik, N. I., Shahzad, M., Ahmad, M., Shahid, M., Feng, X. L., & Guo, J. (2022). Determinants of infant young child feeding among mothers of malnourished children in South Punjab, Pakistan: A qualitative study. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 10, 834089.
 6. Owino, V. O., Murphy-Alford, A. J., Kerac, M., Bahwere, P., Friis, H., Berkley, J. A., & Jackson, A. A. (2019). Measuring growth and medium-and longer-term outcomes in malnourished children. *Maternal & child nutrition*, 15(3), e12790.
 7. Mate, A., Reyes-Goya, C., Santana-Garrido, Á., & Vázquez, C. M. (2021). Lifestyle, maternal nutrition and healthy pregnancy. *Current vascular pharmacology*, 19(2), 132-140.
 8. Nurahmawati, D., Salimo, H., & Dewi, Y. L. R. (2017). Effects of maternal education, psychosocial stress, nutritional status at pregnancy, and family income, on birthweight in Nganjuk, East Java. *Journal of Maternal and Child Health*, 2(4), 324-334.
 9. Warwick, D. P. (2023). Culture and the management of family planning programs. *Medical Anthropology*, 359-376
 10. Nguyen, P. H., Frongillo, E. A., Sanghvi, T., Wable, G., Mahmud, Z., Tran, L. M., ... & Menon, P. (2018). Engagement of husbands in a maternal nutrition program substantially contributed to greater intake of micronutrient supplements and dietary diversity during pregnancy: results of a cluster-randomized program evaluation in Bangladesh. *The Journal of nutrition*, 148(8), 1352-1363.
 11. Ho, A., Flynn, A. C., & Pasupathy, D. (2016). Nutrition in pregnancy. *Obstetrics, Gynaecology & Reproductive Medicine*, 26(9), 259-264.
 12. Steketee, R. W. (2003). Pregnancy, nutrition and parasitic diseases. *The Journal of nutrition*, 133(5), 1661S-1667S.
 13. Earner-Byrne, L. (2017). Mother and child: Maternity and child welfare in Dublin 1922–60. In *Mother and child*. Manchester University Press.
 14. Bergeron, K., Abdi, S., DeCorby, K., Mensah, G., Rempel, B., & Manson, H. (2017). Theories, models and frameworks used in capacity building interventions relevant to public health: a systematic review. *BMC public health*, 17, 1-12.
 15. Pratiwi, A. E., & Sukmawati, N. M. H. (2023). Characteristics of maternal pregnancy and childbirth in payangan sub-sub-district, bali. *Jurnal widya medika*, 9(1), 1-12.
 16. Silk, J., & Romero, D. (2014). The role of parents and families in teen pregnancy prevention: An analysis of programs and policies. *Journal of Family Issues*, 35(10), 1339-1362.
 17. Wolfson, L., Schmidt, R. A., Stinson, J., & Poole, N. (2021). Examining barriers to harm reduction and child welfare services for pregnant women and mothers who use substances using a stigma action framework. *Health*

- & *Social Care in the Community*, 29(3), 589-601.
18. Subrata, T., Bayuningrat, I. G. M., Kartinawati, K. M., Pradnyawati, L. G., Wijaya, M. I., Pariartha, I. M., ... & Sari, L. P. E. K. (2022). PentaCOME 1000+ to Stop Stunting at Payangan District. *Community Development Journal*, 6(3), 67-71.
 19. Pradnyawati, L., & Prabandari, A. A. S. M. (2023, April). Overview of The Achievement Level of Specific and Sensitive Indicators in The First 1000 Days of Life in Tegallalang District. In *Proceedings of the 2nd Warmadewa International Conference on Science, Technology and Humanity, WICSTH 2022, 28-29 October 2022, Denpasar-Bali, Indonesia*.